

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B370
 Date: 12 May 2008
 Take Off: 08:05:16Z
 Landing: 12:36:31Z
 Flight Time 4h31m15s

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: N Germany, Netherlands & UK Operating Area D

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Megan Northway	University of Reading	y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	Cloud Physics / CGPS / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM	y
7	CCN	Steve Cowan	FAAM	
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP/ Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Y/n/y/n
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / TDLAS / Core Chem	Alan Woolley	FAAM	Y
13	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester	

Flight Track:

B370 Track 12-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B370
 Date: 12 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: N Sea, Netherlands, N Germany

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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064515		Start-Up	1.8 kft	001	48'04.68N, 11'17.53E
075902	080143	Pirouette 1	1.8 kft	042	Start 040 left
080516		T/O	3.1 kft	222	Oberpfaffenhofen
080715		Event	4.4 kft	127	Zero JW & Nevz
081342		Video	15.6 kft	353	Start FFC & DFC
094332		Video	20.8 kft	354	Change tapes
095031	095707	Profile 1	10.0 - 4.0 kft	190	To 50', QNH 1018hPa
095859	100032	Profile 1	4.0 - 2.8 kft	016	4k'-2k'
100044	100546	Profile 1	2.7 - 0.23 kft	009	2k', 500fpm Int 500'
100718	100831	Profile 1	0.41 - -.19 kft	193	To 50'
100845	101603	Profile 2	-.12 - 5.0 kft	188	From 50', Q1024
101407		Event	3.2 kft	172	1kfpm from 3k'
101604	102404	Run 1	5.0 kft	177	
102252		Heimann	5.0 kft	175	Cal
102405	102700	Profile 3.1	5.0 - 8.0 kft	175	
102700	103245	Profile 3.2	8.0 - 2.7 kft	174	To 3k'
103319	103904	Profile 3.2	2.4 - -.12 kft	149	3k'-50', Q1021, 500fpm
103904	104433	Profile 3.3	-.12 - 3.4 kft	144	50-3k', Q1018
104457	104726	Profile 3.3	3.4 - 5.0 kft	139	From 3k'
104726	112518	Run 2	5.0 kft	134	
105553		Waypoint	5.0 kft	134	J2
110306		Waypoint	5.0 kft	076	Abeam F1/G1/J1
110945		Waypoint	5.0 kft	072	Abeam D1/F2
111454		Video	5.0 kft	008	Change Tapes
111621		Waypoint	5.0 kft	055	Abeam D2
111835		Event	5.0 kft	076	Zero JW & Nevz
112519	113137	Profile 4.1	5.0 - 11.1 kft	074	1kfpm
113357		Event	11.0 kft	076	Zero Nevz
114128	115056	Profile 4.2	11.0 - 1.9 kft	076	To 2k' on Q1019
115057	120545	Run 3	1.9 kft	075	2k'
115401		Waypoint	1.8 kft	073	Near D3
120521		Waypoint	1.8 kft	078	D4
120545	121015	Profile 5	1.9 - 6.0 kft	093	From 2k'
121016	122732	Run 4	6.0 kft	092	
121813		Waypoint	6.0 kft	084	D5
123631		Land	-.04 kft	241	Rostock-Laage
124543		ASP	-.04 kft	041	Close
124607		Shutdown	-.04 kft	041	53'54.86N, 12'17.10E

B370 Track 12-MAY-08

EUCAARI Flight B370
FAAM sortie brief

Monday 12th May, 2008

- | | |
|---|-------------------------------|
| 1. Pilot 1 (Directflight) – Alan Foster | Power on at: 4:00Z (6 L) |
| 2. Pilot 2 (Directflight) – Ian Ramsay-Rae | Take off: 8:00Z (10 L) |
| 3. CCM (Directflight) – Dawn Quinn | Land Rostok: 12:26 Z (14:26L) |
| 4. Core Chemistry/PAN – Alan Wooley | |
| 5. Flight Manager – Maureen Smith | |
| 6. CloudPhys/CCM2 – Jim Crawford | |
| 7. AMS – Will Morgan | |
| 8. CCN – Steve Cowen | |
| 9. SP2 – Dantong Liu | |
| 10. SWS/SHIMS – Debbie O’Sullivan | |
| 11. Wet Neph – James Bowles | |
| 12. Mission Scientist 1– Hugh Coe | |
| 13. Mission Scientist 2– Megan Northway | |
| 14. Mission Scientist 3 – Stratos Bourtsoukidis | |

Operating Area:

UK operating area D, Holland, Northern Germany

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of fresh and aged pollution in the boundary layer centred over the UK and Europe. Conduct low level over sea for radiation if no cirrus.

Weather:

High pressure over northern Germany/Denmark/Holland with lows southwest of Iceland and over Finland bringing showers and possible aerosol rainout over N. Scandinavia. High pollution over the UK predicted in the boundary layer.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies and no delays prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Oberpfaffenhofen at 8:00Z
3. Transit northwest to point GIGUL in the North Sea at FL240. [1 hr 45 minutes, T=9:44Z]
4. Descend to 55 °N 3 °E, turn towards waypoint 84 and descend to FL090 to begin a profile descent to 50 feet a.s.l. (1000 ft/min above 3000 ft and 500 ft/min below 3000 feet). [20 min, T= 10:04Z]
5. Profile ascent to max aerosol layer and continue to point 84 on south heading. [9 min, T=10:13Z]
6. From point 84 continue towards Rotterdam (J2) at same altitude. [12 min, T=10:25]
7. After 12 minute run, conduct a profile sawtooth beginning descent to 50 ft followed by profile ascent to FL90 and descend to 2000 ft a.g.l. at point J2 (Rotterdam). [24 min, T=10:49Z]
8. Conduct an SLR at 2000 ft a.g.l east over northern Germany through waypoints (D1/F2 -> D2 -> D3-> D4 -> D5 - Rostok with 1-2 sawtooth profiles from 2000 ft a.g.l. to FL90 between D2 and D4. [1 hr 37 min, 12:26Z].
9. Profile descent to Rostock-Laage for refuel, landing at 12:26Z. [Total time 4 hr, 26 min]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B390** Date 12 May 2008 Name Megan Northrup Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
7:59:02	—	0 agl 2000a.sl	040	48°04.68N 111°17.53E	360° turn pirouette - perfectly clear skies end of pirouette (1/2 more pirouette to center for To Ooperpaffen hofen ^{runway})
15min 8:06:26					Interesting profile in neph on T/O
8:16					
8:37Z		FL 240			A lot of traffic out here. Routing was changed by ATC
9:16		240			Cirrus over head now
9:18		240			passing Amsterdam on left
9:42		FL210			Preparing for descent - stratus deck ahead. maybe -1500ft - profile over clear area
9:42		FL210			cloud physics picking up ice, SPZ seeing BC
9:47		FL130			between 2 layers of cloud ^{Cirrus above} _{stratus below} cloud physics saw 56/L small ice at FL220
9:49		FL100	191		going around stratus for descent broken
09:50:31	P1	FL100 - 4000ft	191	54°12.0N 3°06.0E	tooth profile to 50 ft
9:56	P1	4900			AMS moving - hazy conditions - hard to see horizon

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.370** Date 12 May 2008 Name Megan Northrup Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:57	P1				interrupt P1 at 4000ft
	P1				 corr w/ humidity 2 air masses
10:06	P1				interrupt at 500ft - cloud below us - sea was fog to surface
		5000			climbing to 5000ft max aerosol layer
10:16:04	R1	5000ft			~8 minute run at 5000ft; filter started
10:21:05	and R1 Start of P2	5000 8000ft			
10:26:31	P2	5000-8000ft			passed ^{thru} some light cloud stacks
10:30	P2	5000			 filters were still on
10:31		5000-			passing Mofix
					decreasing alt. sawtooth 5000
10:32		3000ft			500ft/min descent
10:34					A lot of ^{container} ships out here
10:38		220ft			rig to right
10:40		50ft			bird at end at 50ft - bank ^{right}
					AMS peaked at 50ft a few seconds close to saturation on nephigram - we got to the top of saturation layer mixed adiabatic layer to 8300ft
10:45		3700			shipping yard to right

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** ³⁷⁰ ~~100~~ Date 12 May 2008 Name Megan Northway Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:44:57	R3.3	3000-5000	135		patchy cirrus around meso-layer? - but generally clear here
10:47:26 10:50	R2	5000	134		Crossing over Rotterdam at 5000ft. - big city
					Passed J2
11:09	R2	5000			D1/F2 passing
11:13	R2	5000	312		a lot of turbulence - prob maybe just near the top of inversion layers
					(strat-cume) clouds just above us
11:16		5000	72		turn, passing D2
11:16	R2	5000	74		neph climbing → NOx climbing
					2/8 strat cume ahead, above
11:22	R2	5000			A LOT of traffic around - VOX is re very busy - can't climb/descend
	P4.1	5000-FL110			Profile climb - PSAP gates
11:24	P4.1				through cloud strat/cume - PSAP closed
11:28	P4.1				cloud base FL080
11:29	P4.1	FL090	76		out of cloud, little more.
11:31:37	end 4.1	FL110			end of P4.1
11:36:00		FL110	76		holding at FL110

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.370** Date 12 May 2008 Name Megan Northway Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:44	P4.2	110-2000	76	52.7N 8.1E	clear ahead - PSAP valve open - but probably near H ₂ O saturation
11:46	P4.2				turbulent ^{# 6000-9000 ft} 10
11:50:52	R3	2000			D3 - D4 kft
					passing D4 2 -
	PS	2000-5000			profite
	PS				partitioning nitrate, i equilibrium w/ RH growth above 5/6 kft w/ humidity → increase in scattering
12:09	PS	4500			NO ₃ (AMS) increased 2-3 fold
12:10:16	end of PS start R4	6000	76		cloud above / turbulence, just
12:12	R4	6000	76		below base; filter open for R4
12:18					passing D6, turn left
12:26					end of filter
12:27:32	R4	6000	76		end of run
12:29		6000- grd.	-		Descend into Rostok-Lage
~ 12:34					Land Rostok-Lage no pirouette ^{cloud} cirrus above

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**..... Date 12/5/08 Name HUGH COE Page 3 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:16:04	end P2 start P3	5000'			SLR ~ 50M ⁻¹ σ _{blue} 1 μg m ⁻³ NO ₃ ; 2 μg m ⁻³ SO ₄
10:24:05	end P1	5000' FL080			Ascent Nph stayed higher up to FL080 close to further to South and Datal coast → level with Norfolk, VA
10:28	end P3 start P4	FL080 → 5000'			Profile up to down to 5000' Flies 0 ft now.
10:30					SmPS manometer all way down aged. 0.16 μg m ⁻³ NO ₃ 1.9 μg m ⁻³ SO ₃ SO ₃ 4 μg m ⁻³ org
10:39:17	END P4	50 ft			
10:39:17	PS CLIMB				NO ₃ 4 μg m ⁻³ 1 μg m ⁻³ SO ₂ some SO ₂ and NO _x 'Ship plume' ? Past container ships. Very enhanced layer close to surface. Last thermodynamic profile shows nearly saturated at FL080

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.370** Date ...12/15/08 Name **MUGHCEE** Page ...4.. of ...6...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:47					high cirrus add Cu FL090 - FL100 to north of Rattler - to south side are clear except for cirrus (as per Captain).
10:47:26	22. ²¹⁰³³	FL050			Start of run. previous profiles are similar over N Sea but thermodynamic shows we have a very shallow shallow layer at surface - polluted and nearly subsided into an adiabatic layer to FL080 nearly sat at top.
10:51:47					NO _x 2.3 ppb in main layer
10:52:56					Much clearer inland at 5000ft. Some small Cu to north and south but v scattered.
11:08:48		FL050			Turbulent; θ varying a lot; correlated with NO ₂ scattering and NO _x $\Rightarrow$ prob sitting at top of BL and being mixed at BL top.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...370** Date 12/5/08 Name HUGH CCE Page 5 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:16:30		FLO80			At 02 just below clouds scattered cu. Still quite bumpy, θ changing a lot.
11:25:17	END R2 START P1	FLO80 → F410			Cloud base FLO80. High nitrate and but big unc in sulphate → high neph also cloud processing. v dry layer above.
11:31:38 11:32:38	END P41	F410 ca			Cloud deck now extensive end profile climb.
11:45:18	PROFILE P4.2	F410 → 2000'			Descent profile out of cloud and shows little aerosol in layer. But at 8000' agrees with previous:
11:50:55	END P4.2 START P5	2000'			Descent low scattering but high conc ² of BC (SP2). During last descent profile Nitrate reduced from high to low values as layer dried sulphate not as constant and acidobatically mixed from 2000 - 8000 ft. Dry layer above that

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 370

Date: 12/05/08	Operator: jc	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: 0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	Post take off 08 11 48 ffssp recording on 2dp s noisy – switched off sdc ok pcasp flow ok volts 7.7 sid 1 b370-1.srd																
	081348 transit to operating area																
	Cmd1d 1 1 is flagged as motor on , heater on but heater does not come on Cmd1d 1 0 is flagged as motor off , heater on but motor is on and heater is on																
094120	60		7	100		50										FI220	
095030	70		8	1		0	0									Start profile 1 fl 010	
	65		8	1		0	0									FI090	
	90		8	1		0	0									FI080	
	150		8	1		0	0									FI070	
	1500		8	3		0	0									FI060	
	1750		8	3		0	0									FI050	
	1700		8	3		0	0									FI040	
	1000		8	3		0	0									FI030	
	1000		8	3		0	0									FI020	
	1200		8	3		0	0									FI010	
	2900		9	5		0	0									50ft end p1 start p2	
	900		9	3		0	0									FI010	
	650		9	3		0	0									FI020	
	670		9	3		0	0									FI030	
	930		9	3		0	0									FI040	
	1200		9	3		0	0									FI050	
																Start run 1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.8	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 0.8	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.7		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = 1.0	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 2.6		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 370

Date: 12/05/08	Operator: jc	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: 0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
101800	1150		9	3		0	0										
102000	1200		9	3		0	0										
102200	1080		9	3		0	0										
102400	1100		10	3		0	0									End run 1 start p3.1	
	700		10	3		0	0									FI060	
	720		10	5		0	0									FI070	
	320		10	3		0	0									FI080 end p3.1 start p3.2	
	1100		10	3		0	0									FI070	
	1100		10	3		0	0									FI060	
	1100		10	3		0	0									FI050	
	1300		10	3		0	0									FI040	
	1300		10	3		0	0									FI030	
	1250		10	3		0	0									FI020	
	1000		10	3		0	0									FI010	
	2300		10	3		0	0									50ft end p3.2 start p3.3	
	1050		10	3		0	0									FI010	
	780		11	3		0	0									FI020	
	640		11	3		0	0									FI030	
	520		12	3		0	0									FI040	
	450		12	3		0	0									FI050 end p 3.3, start run 2	
105000	500		12	3		0	0										
105200	500		12	3		0	0										
105400	640		12	3		0	0										
105600	600		12	3		0	0										
110000	640		12	3		0	0										
110200	550		12	3		0	0										
110500	800		12	3		0	0										
111000	1000		13	3		0	0										
111500	700		13	3		0	0										
112000	1100		13	3		0	0										
112500	1300		14	3		0	0										
																End run 2 start p4.1	
	800		14	3		0	0									FI060	
	700		14	3		0	0									FI070	
	1000		187	3000		0	0									FI080	
	400		598	1		0	0									FI090	
	20		641	0		0	0									FI100	
																End p 4.1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.8	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 0.8	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.7		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = 1.0	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 2.6		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 370

Date: 12/05/08	Operator: jc	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: 0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
114128	20		641	0		0	0									P 4.2	
	50		641	0		0	0									FI090	
	1200		641	3		0	0									FI080	
	750		641	3		0	0									FI070	
	1100		641	3		0	0									FI060	
	1200		641	3		0	0									FI050	
	1000		641	3		0	0									FI040	
	1000		641	3		0	0									FI030	
	1000		641	3		0	0									FI020	
115057	1000		641	3		0	0									End p4.2 start r 3	
115500	700		642	3		0	0										
120000	750		642	3		0	0										
120500	750		642	3		0	0									End run 3	
																Start p5 2000ft	
	600		648	3		0	0									FI 020	
	700		648	3		0	0									FI030	
	700		649	3		0	0									FI040	
	650		649	3		0	0									FI050	
	750		649	3		0	0									FI060 end p5 start r4	
121030	1100		649	3		0	0										
121500	750		649	3		0	0										
122200	1000		649	3		0	0										
122500	1050		650	3		0	0										
122732	1000		651	3		0	0									End run 4	
																End science	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.8	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 0.8	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.7		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = 1.0	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 2.6		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B370 **T/O:** 080516
Date of flight: 12 may 2008 **Land:** 123631

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOGFlight number: **B370**

Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 126019
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 35507 Blocks written = 35507 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		No 2dp Start = 080000 End = 124000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 080000 End =124000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =080000 End = 124000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 120432 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B370****Date of Flight:**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	1 1.15	Min size = Vol flow rate = 080000 124000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_proccasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_proccasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B370_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

06:14:41.49 --- - - -
06:14:41.49 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:14:41.49 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:14:41.49 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B370
06:14:41.49 --- - - -
06:14:50.85 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:14:51.78 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:14:55.32 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
06:14:55.89 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
06:14:57.45 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:14:57.73 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:15:12.73 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
06:15:21.08 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:15:23.25 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:15:25.29 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:15:26.52 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:15:28.59 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:15:28.59 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:15:30.43 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:15:32.18 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:15:32.18 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:15:33.75 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:15:35.78 SWS - - 45 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 45ms.
06:15:35.79 SWS - - - 45 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 45ms.
06:15:38.19 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 50ms.
06:15:38.19 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 45ms to 50ms.
06:15:43.84 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:15:43.84 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:15:43.84 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:15:49.02 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:15:53.90 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:15:53.92 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:15:53.92 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:15:54.84 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:15:55.06 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:00.73 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:03.17 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:03.25 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:03.42 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:04.11 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:04.33 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:10.03 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:12.78 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:12.85 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:13.35 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:16:13.74 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:13.93 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:19.77 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:53.79 USH - - - Idling
06:16:53.84 SWS - - - Idling
06:16:54.30 LSH - - - Idling
06:17:00.46 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:17:00.46 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:17:00.47 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:17:01.89 USH - - - Idling
06:17:01.96 SWS - - - Idling
06:17:02.30 LSH - - - Idling
06:18:38.96 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:18:38.96 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:18:38.97 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:18:43.22 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:18:48.63 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:18:48.66 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:18:48.71 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:18:49.58 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:18:49.84 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

06:18:55.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:18:56.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:18:56.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:18:56.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:18:57.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:18:58.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:19:03.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:20:02.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 15 deg
06:22:08.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:22:14.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:22:14.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:22:14.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:22:15.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:22:15.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:22:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:22:16.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:22:17.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:22:17.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:22:20.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:22:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
06:25:37.70	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:25:43.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:43.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:43.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:44.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:25:44.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:25:50.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:25:55.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
06:25:57.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:57.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:57.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:25:58.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:25:58.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:26:04.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:26:20.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** shims being cleaned
06:27:19.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** (USH)
06:28:33.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** lower shims being cleaned
06:29:02.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
06:29:46.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** LSH being cleaned
06:31:34.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
06:32:48.24	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:32:52.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:32:53.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:32:53.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:32:53.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:32:54.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:32:59.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:33:01.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:01.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:01.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:02.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:33:02.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:33:08.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:34:39.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
06:34:48.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:34:54.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:34:54.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:34:54.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:34:55.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:34:55.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:35:00.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:35:03.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:35:03.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:35:04.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:35:04.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:35:04.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:35:10.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:37:29.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
06:40:31.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg

06:42:15.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:42:15.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:42:15.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:42:17.60	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
06:42:19.29	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
06:42:25.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:25.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:25.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:34.25	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:42:38.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:42:38.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:42:38.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:42:39.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:39.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:42:43.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:42:44.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:44.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:42:45.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:47.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
06:47:39.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** cleaned sws
06:47:46.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:47:46.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:47:46.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:47:49.25	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
06:47:50.94	SWS	-4.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
06:47:52.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:47:52.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:47:52.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:47:58.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
06:52:29.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler 5 deg
06:54:29.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
06:56:02.32	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:56:07.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:07.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:07.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:08.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:56:08.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:56:14.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:56:20.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:20.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:20.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:56:21.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:56:21.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:56:27.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:57:56.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
06:58:05.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:06.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:58:07.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:08.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:58:10.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:16.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:29.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:02:33.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:02:33.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:02:33.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:02:34.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:34.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:36.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:02:37.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:02:37.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:38.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:40.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:18:57.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
07:39:46.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3
07:42:57.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -4
07:43:02.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:43:03.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:04.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

07:43:05.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:06.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:43:12.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:53.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** -3
07:48:54.04	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.400
07:51:19.76	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:51:24.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:24.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:24.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:25.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:25.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:31.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:40.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:40.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:40.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:41.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:41.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:47.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:25.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:25.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:25.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:26.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:26.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:31.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:31.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:32.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:32.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:03.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** p1
07:59:34.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 360 piroeutte on heading 40?
08:01:44.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of pirouette 1
08:08:31.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2 deg
08:08:39.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:08:44.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:08:44.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:08:44.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:08:45.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:45.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:51.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:03.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:03.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:04.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:04.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:04.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:10.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:10:54.02	SWS	-0.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:10:58.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:10:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:10:58.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:10:59.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:10:59.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:05.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:30.35	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
08:11:30.35	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
08:11:32.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:34.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:35.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:36.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:37.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:38.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:08.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:08.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:08.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:09.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:09.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:15.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:19.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:19.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:19.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

08:24:20.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:20.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:26.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:34:08.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear skies
08:34:26.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** above some contrails and scatters
cumulonimbus below						
08:43:10.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:10.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:10.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:11.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:12.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:16.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:33.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:33.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:33.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:34.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:35.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:40.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:45.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
08:43:55.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:55.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:56.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:57.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:57.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:02.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:03.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:44:03.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:44:04.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:44:04.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:05.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:10.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:10.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
08:48:14.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
08:49:17.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:17.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:18.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:19.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:24.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:34.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:35.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:35.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:35.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:36.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:37.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:37.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:38.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:39.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:42.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:45.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
08:59:43.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:59:45.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:59:45.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:59:46.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:59:47.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:59:54.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:59:58.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
09:01:30.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:31.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:32.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:33.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:58.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:02:03.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:03.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:03.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:04.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:05.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:10.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:54.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 0 deg

09:06:06.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:06.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:06.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:07.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:08.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:13.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:38.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
09:07:29.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:29.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:29.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:29.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:07:30.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:07:35.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:08:50.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cumulus to left and right of plane but not directly below
09:20:14.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1
09:30:10.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:10.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:10.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:11.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:12.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:17.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:31:14.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above
09:33:55.02	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
09:33:55.03	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
09:33:56.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:57.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:59.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:00.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:05.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:05.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:05.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:05.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:06.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:08.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:08.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:34:09.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:09.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:12.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:42.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** wide spread stratocumulus,
09:34:51.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** high low and med cloud
09:40:22.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** low level status ahead of aircraft will run into around a couple of thousand feet
09:46:54.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** layer of thick cirrus above
09:47:25.11	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
09:47:25.14	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
09:47:28.44	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
09:47:28.46	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
09:47:29.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:47:30.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:47:31.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:47:31.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:31.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 1
09:50:51.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** down to 4000 ft from FL100
09:53:42.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** p1 interupt
09:57:09.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL 40 p1 interupt now
09:59:06.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** p1 restart
10:05:47.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** interupt at 500 ft
10:07:20.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** resatrt p1
10:08:32.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
10:15:10.33	---	-	-	-	-	***
10:16:05.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1
10:18:34.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:34.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:34.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:38.05	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.500
10:18:39.82	SWS	174.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:18:44.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:44.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:18:44.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:46.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:46.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:47.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:47.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:47.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:53.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:55.11	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
10:18:55.14	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
10:18:56.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:57.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:59.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:00.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:01.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:02.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:45.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:47.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:47.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:48.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:48.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:49.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:54.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:09.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of r
10:24:16.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
10:27:13.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
10:29:12.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:12.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:13.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:13.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:14.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:19.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:39.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3000 ft
10:34:40.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** still a large amount of cloud around
10:38:04.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 500 ft
10:39:05.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft start of profile ascent
10:44:35.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p1
10:44:40.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 3500 ft
10:44:59.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:59.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:59.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:02.44	SWS	174.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
10:45:04.25	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:45:06.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:06.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:06.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:11.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile ascent
10:45:22.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:22.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:22.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:23.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:28.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:21.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** high cirrus and odd patch of q around inversion
10:46:28.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** at around FL 90
10:46:51.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** but near dutch coast skies are clear apart from cirrus
10:47:29.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
10:48:21.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** lots and lots of ships below
10:48:53.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:53.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:54.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:54.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:54.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:55.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:59.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:00.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:01.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:49:02.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:04.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:05.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:07.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:14.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:01.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** about to go over land (leaving sea)
10:50:46.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** flying over coast now
10:52:40.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
10:54:48.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
10:55:59.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning
11:02:56.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** trurning
11:04:34.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
11:09:41.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** turn at D1/F2
11:10:57.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
11:12:42.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:13:32.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:13:42.83	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:13:42.86	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:13:44.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:45.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:46.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:47.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:48.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:48.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:50.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:51.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:59.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** -1
11:17:41.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:46.58	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
11:17:46.61	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
11:17:48.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:48.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:50.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:51.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:52.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:53.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:20:06.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
11:25:22.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** pro
11:25:40.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2 satrt of profile 4.1
11:28:14.20	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
11:28:14.23	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
11:28:16.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:16.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:17.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:18.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:20.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:21.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:33.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloudf
11:28:39.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base FL 80
11:29:16.23	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
11:29:16.25	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
11:29:18.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:20.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:22.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:25.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:28.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:28.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:29.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:29.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:29.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:31.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:43.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p
11:32:31.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:31.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:31.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:33.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:33.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:34.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:32:39.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:39.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:39.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:40.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:42.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:49.69	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
11:32:49.71	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
11:32:51.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:52.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:53.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:54.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:56.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:56.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:57.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:57.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:58.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:59.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:44.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
11:37:59.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:59.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:59.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:00.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:00.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:01.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:32.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:32.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:32.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:33.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:33.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:35.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:02.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** thick sheet of atrato q just below
11:39:11.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:11.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:12.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:12.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:13.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:17.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:17.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:17.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:18.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:18.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:19.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:32.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** p d now
11:41:43.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 4.2
11:47:54.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:54.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:54.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:54.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:55.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:57.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:06.05	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
11:48:06.09	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
11:48:12.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:13.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:16.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:17.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:58.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** en d of p d start of run at 2000 ft
12:02:56.52	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:02:56.54	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:02:58.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:59.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:00.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:01.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:02.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:03.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:03.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:03.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:03:04.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:05.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:12.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:12.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:12.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:13.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:13.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:14.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:22.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** D4
12:05:46.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run climbing to 5000ft
12:09:12.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** -2
12:10:17.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run end of profile climb
12:13:28.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:28.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:29.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:30.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:30.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:31.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:33.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:33.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:33.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:34.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:34.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:35.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:30.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** D5
12:18:38.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** flying through bottom of cloud base
12:27:42.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of descent before landing
12:28:32.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:32.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:32.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:33.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:33.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:35.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Flight:

B370

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS)

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B370

Date: 12 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not run
2. Digital Video Box – stickle brick no longer holding it up, now resting on keyboard at aft CorCon
3. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.
4. GIN – pre-flight, hdg and positions going in opposite directions. Reset power then okay.

Instrument Status roundup

SWS – Okay

Cloud Physics – 2DP off, otherwise okay

CGPS – wouldn't lock in to flight mode so couldn't calibrate it.

SP2 – Okay, CAPS

CAPS/CPI /2DS – not run

Neph/PSAP/Filters/CVI – Filters “old” 10um packs no flow, “new” ones okay

AMS – Online “0942Z, just before start of science. Organics not as good as they should be but inorganics good.

SMPS – okay at low level

CCN – okay

PAN/ Tdlas/Core Chem – okay

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 12/15/08

Flight No: B 370

Pre-Flighter: *AW*

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU <i>Ground</i>	Align	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	<i>ffc above, but no cleaning access</i>
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☐	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☐	INU	Navigate then back to Align	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
25	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
26	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
28	☐			
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	<i>not lke</i>
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☐	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
44	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B370:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Megan Northway
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log. CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378
PAN	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b370_095417_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b370_105417_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b370_115417_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b370_075409_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b370_085409_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b370_095409_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b370_105409_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b370_115409_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b370_075411_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b370_085411_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b370_095411_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b370_105411_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b370_115411_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b370_075414_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b370_085414_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b370_095414_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b370_105414_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b370_115414_1hz.avi

The conversion program crashed in the following files:-
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b370_075417_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b370_085417_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Hugh Coe

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The University of Manchester
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Oxford Road
Manchester
M13 9PL

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